

Biodiversity, a tool and resource for supporting the development of regional management and sustainable development plans.

Case Study: The Superfamily Papilionoidea (Order Lepidoptera) in the Pogradec Region.

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Abstract

Biodiversity is a key component of natural heritage, which should play an important role in the process of developing regional plans for sustainable management and development. This study focuses on the biodiversity of the Papilionoidea superfamily (Order Lepidoptera) in the Pogradec region and aims to show how the knowledge and distribution of species diversity can contribute to the development of policies and plans that support nature conservation and sustainable tourism. The Pogradec region, with an area of around 594 km², is an area of significant importance for biodiversity in Albania, where 132 butterfly species from 6 families, part of the Papilionoidea superfamily, have been historically identified. New observations from 2024 confirmed the presence of 19 butterfly species, representing 14% of the historical data, including a new species, *Thymelicus sylvestris* (Poda, 1761). The number of species collected during this field trip is low compared to the biodiversity of the areas, as the trip was focused only on lower altitudes. The altitude at which the material was collected is a limiting factor for the range of species observed. We expect the number of species to be higher at higher altitudes, but this monitoring will be the focus of next year's study. Butterflies, as bio-indicators of the environment, help in identifying natural habitats and can serve as a reference point for the development of sustainable tourism. Observing butterflies as part of activities related to ecotourism can bring economic opportunities to local communities, contributing to sustainable development and the preservation of biodiversity.

Key words

Biodiversity, Papilionoidea, Lepidoptera, sustainable development, regional development plans, ecosystem management, Pogradec, Albania.

Introduction

The history of Lepidoptera studies in Albania spans from the beginning of the last century, involving local and foreign researchers and entomologists continuously contributing to the discovery of new species for the country's fauna and enhancing knowledge about these species and their distribution and ecological needs (Cuvelier *et al.* 2018; Cuvelier *et al.* 2023). The first publications were made at the beginning of the 20th century by foreign authors, followed by contributions from both foreign and local authors (Beshkov 1995; Beshkov & Misja 1995; Beshkov *et al.* 1996). In recent years, there has been increased interest not only in Lepidoptera but in biodiversity in general. As a direct contribution, we now have distribution maps of butterflies for Albania, new species, and confirmations for species with data deficiencies or absences (Cuvelier *et al.* 2018; Cuvelier *et al.* 2023). Studies on Albania confirm 208 species of butterflies known for Albania, with a potential of encountering around 10 - 15 additional species that have not yet been discovered (Cuvelier *et al.*, 2023). The Pogradec region, located in the southeastern part of Albania, covering approximately 584 km², stands out for its landscape diversity and the richness of its flora and fauna. Historically identified Papilionoidea for this area includes 132 species belonging to 6 families. In 2024, the butterfly species list for the Pogradec area was enriched with a new species, *Thymelicus sylvestris* (Poda, 1761). With this new finding, the total number of species reaches 133, and it is likely that other species may still be discovered in the area. An important component as a tool and resource for supporting the drafting of regional management plans is the integration of natural resources and scientific knowledge into regional development policies and strategies. This process is essential for ensuring sustainable management of natural resources and promoting regional economic development in harmony with biodiversity conservation. Local butterfly tours as part of ecotourism can serve as an income source for local communities, creating more opportunities for sustainable economic development. Integrating this knowledge into regional policies and development strategies can create new opportunities for economic activities and biodiversity protection.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The collection of biological material in the Pogradec region was carried out in 5 main stations: Pogradec Castle, the Christian Basilica in Lin village, Archaeological discoveries in Buqezë village, Selca Tombs and Guri i Kamjes.

• Pogradec Castle (Fig. 1-2)

(40.908650°N 20.646233°E according to Google Earth version 7.1) located near Beragozhd village in the Dardhas administrative unit, at an altitude of 880 meters above sea level (Krog *et al.* 2013).

• Christian Basilica in Lin village (Fig. 3-4)

41.066000°N 20.644500°E according to Google Earth version 7.1) located on the Lin peninsula, 22 km away from Pogradec city, at an altitude of 730 meters above sea level.

The area features a glacial environment interspersed with basic volcanic rocks from the Middle Triassic period. It also includes herbaceous plants in grasslands within openings of *Ostrya carpinifolia* and oaks, surrounded by shrubs of *Ruscus* and *Juniperus* (Krog *et al.* 2013).

• Archaeological discoveries in Buqezë village

41.046650°N 20.633217°E according to Google Earth version 7.1) where the terrain is a combination of lowlands and mountainous areas with exceptional wealth at an altitude of 696 m. This area is rich in various species of insects and small animals, important for the preservation of the lake's ecosystem and its surrounding areas (Krog *et al.* 2013).

• Selca Tombs

40.990200°N 20.520450°E according to Google Earth version 7.1) part of an ecosystem where chestnut and beech forests are common, creating a rich habitat for various insect species. Located at an altitude of 720 meters above sea level (Krog *et al.* 2013).

• Guri i Kamjes

40.836933°N 20.615067°E according to Google Earth version 7.1) near Beragozhd village in the Dardhas administrative unit, close to Qafa e Lipovës, at an altitude of 1,461 m above sea level.

Its habitat consists of sandy-conglomerate rocks in openings within beech forests.

This area is rich in dense forests and shrubs, with a high biodiversity including various species of trees and wild plants (Krog *et al.* 2013).

Collection and preservation of materials

The collection of butterfly samples was carried out using aerial entomological nets made of nylon, with a diameter of 30 cm and a length of 70-80 cm, attached to a wooden or metal handle of 100 cm (Paparisto & Misja 2005) between 09:00 and 18:00, with variations depending on the climate and season. The collected material in the field was stored dry during the study period. Before starting the identification process, the individuals were softened by placing them on absorbent paper, in a standard glass desiccator with a 40 cm diameter reservoir filled with water at 100°C, where they remained in a vacuum state for 24 hours. After softening, the individuals underwent a mounting procedure. The mounted material was dried at room temperature (18-23°C) for about 3 to 4 weeks (Paparisto & Misja 2005).

During the field work, it is important to record detailed data, including GPS coordinates, dates, habitat descriptions, photographs of habitats and collected or observed species in the field, etc. (Paparisto & Misja 2005). Each specimen carries a label containing the scientific name, collection location, collection date, and identifier's name (A.K. Walker *et al.* 1999). To ensure data accuracy, a control process is implemented by a group of taxonomists (Turner *et al.* 2001).

Digital photographs were taken for each specimen, providing a permanent data record serving as a long-term reference. The databases created, serve as a data source for implementing regional management and sustainable development plans. To organize the collected data (Magurran 2013), Microsoft Excel was used. Insects collected for long-term preservation were placed in entomological boxes with dimensions of 70 x 60 cm with a depth of 10 cm, stored in a cool, dry, and dark place to minimize degradation (Emmel 1973). Each entomological box with biological material is accompanied by the corresponding serial number and the name of the identifier (Paparisto & Misja 2005).

Fig. 1-2. Pogradec Castle (© Anila Paparisto)
 Fig. 3. Christian Basilica, Lin village (© Anila Paparisto)

Fig. 4. Christian Basilica, Lin village (© Anila Paparisto)
 Fig. 5-6. Guri i Kamjes (© Anila Paparisto)

Results and discussion

This study presents the list of all Lepidoptera species in the Pogradec area at 5 collection stations. From the taxonomic determination of 57 individuals collected in 2024, we report for the Pogradec area, 19 species distributed in 5 families. An analysis of families by number of species (Table 1, Graph 1) shows that the Nymphalidae family presents the highest species diversity, with 9 species or 9.47%, followed by the Lycaenidae family represented by 4 species or 4.21%, Pieridae family 3 species or 3.16%, Papilionidae family 2 species or 2.11%, and the family with the lowest diversity is Hesperidae represented by 1 species or 1.5%.

Table 1. Number of species per family.

No.	Family	Species per family	Percentage of species per family found in Albania
1	Papilionidae	2	2.11%
2	Hesperidae	1	1.5%
3	Pieridae	3	3.16%
4	Lycaenidae	4	4.21%
5	Nymphalidae	9	9.47%

Graph 1. Distribution of families by percentage of counted species (© Xhuliana Qirinxi)

The analysis of the 2024 results reveals that out of the 57 individuals collected, the most frequently observed species is *Melanargia galathea* (Linnaeus, 1758) from the Nymphalidae family (Table 2, Graph 2).

M. galathea was present at all stations, but at Guri i Kamjes, particularly at its base, a population of hundreds of individuals was observed. The timing of the field trip coincided with the post-reproductive period of the population, as all individuals were fresh.

The identification of this species as *Leptidea sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758) is based on external morphological observations.

Without dissection or molecular analysis, it cannot be confirmed with certainty, and there remains a possibility that it could be *Leptidea juvernica* (Williams, 1946).

To date, no definitive evidence has been provided for the presence of *L. juvernica* (Williams, 1946) in this area.

Table 2. Number of specimens encountered per species.

No.	Family	Genus	Species	Number of encountered specimens in 2024
1	Papilionidae	<i>Iphiclides</i>	<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2
2	Papilionidae	<i>Papilio</i>	<i>Papilio machaon</i> Linnaeus, 1758	2
3	Hesperiidae	<i>Thymelicus</i>	<i>Thymelicus sylvestris</i> (Poda, 1761)	3
4	Pieridae	<i>Colias</i>	<i>Colias croceus</i> (Geoffrey, 1785)	6
5	Pieridae	<i>Leptidea</i>	<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1
6	Pieridae	<i>Pieris</i>	<i>Pieris rapae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	7
7	Lycaenidae	<i>Aricia</i>	<i>Aricia agestis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	1
8	Lycaenidae	<i>Plebejus</i>	<i>Plebejus argus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1
9	Lycaenidae	<i>Plebejus</i>	<i>Plebejus idas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	1
10	Lycaenidae	<i>Polyommatus</i>	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	7
11	Nymphalidae	<i>Fabriciana</i>	<i>Fabriciana adippe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	1
12	Nymphalidae	<i>Issoria</i>	<i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1
13	Nymphalidae	<i>Speyeria</i>	<i>Speyeria aglaja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1
14	Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea</i>	<i>Melitaea athalia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	3
15	Nymphalidae	<i>Melitaea</i>	<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, [1778])	4
16	Nymphalidae	<i>Lasiommata</i>	<i>Lasiommata megera</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	1
17	Nymphalidae	<i>Maniola</i>	<i>Maniola jurtina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4
18	Nymphalidae	<i>Melanargia</i>	<i>Melanargia galathea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8
19	Nymphalidae	<i>Melanargia</i>	<i>Melanargia larissa</i> (Geyer, [1828])	3

Graph 2. Number of specimens collected for each species (© Xhuliana Qirinxhi)

During the 2024 expeditions, a new species for the Pogradec area was identified. This brings the total number of known species from 132 to 133. The new species is *Thymelicus sylvestris* (Poda, 1761), recorded at the Guri i Kamjes monitoring station, in Beragozhd village.

This species, according to taxonomic classification, belongs to the Hesperiidae family and the *Thymelicus* genus.

During the study in the Pogradec area, 132 butterfly species had been historically identified. With the discovery of one new species in 2024, the total number of recorded species now stands at 133.

22 species are endangered according to the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Among them, the species *Phengaris arion* (Linnaeus, 1758), has a critical status, highlighting the urgent need for protective measures and habitat preservation (Table 3).

This emphasizes the importance of biodiversity conservation and efforts to protect these endangered species (Cuvelier *et al.*, 2018; 2023).

Table 3. Endangerment status.

Species	Endangerment status 2022	Endangerment status 2016	Endangerment status 2010
<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU B2a	LC	LC
<i>Erynnis marlayi</i> (Boisduval, [1834])	VU	LC	LC
<i>Muschampia floccifera</i> (Zeller, 1847)	VU	LC	NT A2c
<i>Leptidea duponcheli</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	VU B1	LC	LC
<i>Lycaena candens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844])	VU	-	LC
<i>Cupido osiris</i> (Meigen, [1829])	VU B2a	LC	LC
<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i> (Poda, 1761)	VU	LC	LC
<i>Iolana iolas</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1816)	VU	LC	NT A2c
<i>Phengaris arion</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	CR	LC	EN A2bc
<i>Polyommatus damon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU	LC	NT A2c
<i>Polyommatus eros</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	VU	LC	NT A2c
<i>Polyommatus aroaniensis orphicus</i> Kolev, 2005	DD	-	VU B2ab (ii, iii, iv)
<i>Scolitantides orion</i> (Pallas, 1771)	VU	LC	LC
<i>Favonius quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU D1D2	LC	LC
<i>Hamearis lucina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU B2a	LC	LC
<i>Apatura ilia</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU	LC	LC
<i>Apatura iris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU	LC	LC
<i>Argynnis pandora</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU	LC	LC
<i>Brenthis hecate</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	VU	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha leander</i> (Esper, [1784])	VU	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	VU	LC	NT A2c
<i>Pseudochazara amalthea</i> (Fivaldszky, 1845)	VU	LC	LC

Harta e Bashkise Pogradec

Map. Distribution of species by zones (© Sylvain Cuvelier)

Recognizing and identifying key points that constitute biodiversity-rich natural resources represent significant value, not only for nature conservation but also for the economic development of areas through ecotourism. These points are important resources for biodiversity and also coincide with significant areas for cultural and historical tourism, including archaeological and natural monuments. This unique combination creates extraordinary opportunities for the development of integrated tourism, where nature, history, and culture collaborate in synergy to attract a wide audience of visitors, from researchers and ecologists to history enthusiasts and ordinary tourists.

Moreover, the detailed map we have available, which identifies and links these points with archaeological and natural attractions, serves as a powerful tool for planning and managing these resources. This map can be used to create well-defined tourist routes and points where visitors can follow a trail that includes archaeological monuments, significant natural points, and areas with rich biodiversity, offering them a comprehensive experience.

Disseminating information and actively involving nature researchers, environmental organizations, and policymakers is crucial to ensure these points are treated as priorities in regional and national development policies. Through this collaboration, regional authorities and local government should take steps to protect and develop these areas, ensuring a balance between nature conservation and economic development. This development will contribute to the long-term protection of biodiversity and cultural heritage, while also providing a sustainable source of income for the local community. It is essential to emphasize the need for continuous monitoring by nature researchers to make new discoveries and gain a clearer understanding of the long-term status of the selected localities.

Conclusions

In 2024, the identification of a new species, *Thymelicus sylvestris* (Poda, 1761), increased the number of listed species from 132 to 133, underscoring the importance of biodiversity protection. This also emphasizes the need for continuous monitoring and sustainable commitments in fauna conservation, reinforcing the significance of studies to enrich knowledge about ecosystems and their protection.

In the Pogradec area, out of 132 historically identified species, 22 species are classified as endangered according to the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, with one species, *Phengaris arion* (Linnaeus, 1758), listed as critically endangered. This highlights the need for protective measures, as preserving endangered species is essential for the functioning of ecosystems and the continuity of biodiversity.

The combination of natural resources, archaeological monuments, and cultural heritage creates potential for attracting a wide range of visitors and raising awareness about the conservation of these resources.

Biodiversity offers opportunities for sustainable development, stimulating ecotourism and other sustainable economic activities that contribute to environmental conservation.

Integrating biodiversity into regional strategies is key to protecting natural wealth and promoting sustainable economic development.

Activities supported by biodiversity can empower the local economy and create sustainable employment opportunities.

Author contributions

Xhuliana Qirinxi: conceptualisation, field work, analysis, writing - original draft.

Anila Papanisto: conceptualisation, field work, writing - review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, visualisation, writing - review and editing.

Eltjon Halimi: graphical analysis.

Elena Hysi: field work.

Nasiola Teneqexhi: field work.

Supplementary material

S1. Species observations in the Pogradec region: historical, 2017-2024, actual research and Red list 2022 data.

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